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Education reform in Ukraine: unique possibilities and serious risks

*Lidiya Tikhonova*¹, *Olena Turuta*¹, and *Oksana Zhydkova*¹

¹Philosophy Department of Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics, Ukraine

Abstract. Nowadays the national education system is undergoing the crucial period of its development. The state policy in the education sphere is obtaining of the quality education by every citizen throughout his life with further confirmation of its national character. Furthermore, one of the components of the higher education reform is to ensure the advanced innovation-driven development of education, as well as to integrate it into the global education system, taking into consideration the worldwide trends.

1 Introduction

After the declaration of Ukraine's independence, the education has been declared as one of the priorities of social, economic, spiritual and cultural development of the society. The right to free personal development and education has been embodied in The Constitution of Ukraine. From this perspective, it is the extremely important to create the conditions for holistic development of the human being as a personality and society's ultimate value, his/her talents, intellectual, creative, and physical abilities, shaping values and competences required for successful self-realization, raising responsible citizens who can make an informed social choice [1]. After 28 years, the education problems remain the target of great interest for the national educational and pedagogic science and public practice. Most conspicuously the society spiritually and intellectually devolves as well as the state lags behind the progressive economically developed countries in cultural, technical and technological areas without the developed education system, the precise definition of its goals or the appropriate organization of education management.

In 1991, the Ukrainian State had the developed education infrastructure. In accordance with the Law of Ukrainian SSR "On Education" of 23rd of May 1991, the state had 1242 vocational, 735 specialized secondary and 156 higher educational institutions, standard and higher doctorate programs in 300 specialties, 518 advanced training and professional retraining institutions. Statistically, the quantity of the educational institutions was consistent with the level of these institutions in the majority of the developed counties of the world [2, C. 33].

2 Analyses of main aspects of the higher education reform

Conventional wisdom is that formally the higher education reform started after the Law on Higher Education had been passed in 2014. The need of adoption of such a document was caused by the low quality of national education, as it had been repeatedly emphasized by the government officials. Hence, higher educational institutions were out of touch with

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needs of the labor market, the students and teachers were not motivated to improve the quality of the education. The Ministry of Education and Science had discussed the possibility of much-anticipated implementation of the concept of education development till 2020, but the draft froze at the stage of public consultation.

On 22nd of November 2019, the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine adopted as a basis the draft No. 2299, which amended the laws on enhancement of educational activities in the field of higher education [3]. According to the initiators of the draft, it will strengthen the European vector of development of our higher education system and will bridge the gap between our country and the other countries of the Bologna process. Education in higher educational institutions will become student oriented, and the students themselves will be able to influence the quality of educational services and the management of universities. Furthermore, the need to introduce amendments and additions to the Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education" is conditioned primarily by the obligations envisioned by Article 431 of the Association Agreement between the European Union and Ukraine, which involves the reform and modernization of the higher education system, promotion of the convergence in higher education within the framework of the Bologna process, improving the quality of higher education, expansion of opportunities for higher educational institutions, increasing the mobility of students and teachers, cooperation to facilitate the access to higher education, etc. Moreover, in 2015, a new revision of standards and recommendations for quality assurance was introduced in the European Higher Education Area, which also requires the reflection in the legislative framework of higher education [4].

Thus, nowadays education experiences a unique opportunity to make bold decisions. Globalization of life, constant change of technologies, transition from the post-industrial to information society, predetermines the change of attitude towards a person. He has become the main goal, the lever of modern progress. Therefore, one of the main tasks of the state is the advanced innovative development of the educational industry, as well as the creation of conditions for self-affirmation and self-realization of the individual throughout his life.

We will try to analyze the main aspects of the higher education reform, the positive aspects, which it has, and the risks that the higher educational institutions are already experiencing.

At the beginning of the 2018/19 academic year, 652 higher educational institutions operated in Ukraine, the number of specialists released reached 413,000. This is reported by the State Statistics Service of Ukraine [5]. According to various ratings, our country is consistently included in the top 20 countries with the largest number of universities. In Europe, fewer universities are presented, although the criteria for higher educational institutions in Ukraine and in Europe are slightly different.

The Minister of Education and Science, Hanna Novosad, notes that the state does not effectively spend funds on higher education by funding a large network of higher educational institutions, and therefore the Ministry plans to reduce the number of universities. She mentioned this point during her interview to Censor.Net. "As the University is the state-funded educational institution, the administration has no opportunity to stimulate the best. We need to encourage a university, as well as a university administration, to engage the best teachers. Therefore, we need to introduce funding based on the results of the university's activities. That is not the case at the moment. Understandably, the university should be interested in fighting for the best teachers and obviously, it should be interested in rewarding them better. This is exactly the system we want to implement," the Minister said [6].

Indeed, on the one hand, too many universities in the country provide a very doubtful quality of education. On the other hand, the decrease in the number of universities will

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hardly be able to solve the problems that currently exist in the system of higher education. As noted by the Director of The Analytical Center CEDOS Yegor Stadnyj, the institution can be good, having 100 students, and can be mediocre, having 10,000. Moreover, the expert notes that the Government should firstly determine the type of network the country needs, and then propose a list of types of institutions with the description of the objectives for each of them and their funding methods. Based on this, the institutions then should independently identify themselves as a certain type and decide how to achieve the set objectives with a specified amount of funding [7]. Besides, today there is no accurate information about the number of all educational institutions, there is no clear understanding of their material and technical state, logistical accessibility, audit of the quality of education, etc. Only after analyzing all the data, having a full list of educational institutions, can we begin the process of their optimization, particularly in the case of rural areas.

Another key issue of the higher education reform is the change of approach to funding of higher educational institutions. The reform process in the funding sphere was initiated by Serhiy Kvit. He proposed the draft, which was based on three main components: the first is basic (block) financing; the second is the capital expenditure fund; the third is the state support fund. This approach assumed that during its implementation, a rigid relation between such criteria as the size of state funding of universities, the number of students and the number of teachers would be broken. The old funding system was focused primarily on quantitative indicators, at the expense of the quality of education. It was assumed that among the indicators of the university's performance the following criteria should be taken into consideration: the number of scientific publications, research activities, academic mobility, the level of employment of graduates, the attraction of national and foreign sources of funding to scientific research.

Starting from the current year, as a part of the educational reform, the higher educational institutions will be funded according to a formula, in which the universities with better performance receive more funding in comparison to the budget of the previous year. The Cabinet Of Ministers of Ukraine adopted the corresponding decision at the end of December 2019 [8]. The public funding system must decrease year after year and eventually disappear. Instead, the funding system should be based on the universities' activity results. The calculation of the amount of funding was carried out according to the following indicators: the size of the university, the student contingent, the regional ratio, positions of the university in international ratings, the amount of funds for research that the university attracts from business or under international grants. According to Hanna Novosad, Minister of Education and Science, "for the first time, the Ministry of Education and Science published the data on the distribution of public funds between universities and clear criteria for such distribution. Each university received funding based on the results of its work and the incentive to develop more dynamically." [9].

It should be noted that officials have repeatedly stated that universities in Ukraine will become similar to the European ones in the nearest future. However, when asked which model of EU member states would form the basis of the mentioned education reform, no one answered. The main criterion is to differ from the Soviet Union model. Therefore, what does the "Eurostandard" mean for us? Higher educational institutions in Europe with the high ratings differ from post-Soviet universities in the predominance of the research component of their activity. Most of their income is derived from scientific and research works, which have a specific practical application. The national universities are almost completely dependent on the students, which study on a tuition basis. Unfortunately, national universities do not have the ways to make money yet. In case if, according to The Minister of Education and Science Hanna Novosad, the change in the funding system also

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implies a transition to “research universities”, what will happen to the funding of science in Ukraine?

Nowadays, around 0.4% of GDP is allocated to science from the state budget, which is 2.3 billion hryvnias per year. However, according to the MES (The Ministry of Education and Science) [10] the Ukrainian science can count on 0.1% of GDP only. Within the context of knowledge-intensity as a percentage of GDP, Ukraine today is inferior to almost each and every country of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). For example, in 2016 Ukraine fell to the 42nd place in the rating of innovative economies, next to Serbia, Tunisia, Thailand [11]. It could not be denied that Ukrainian science should be integrated into the real sector of the economy, the existing achievements should be applied, and this is possible only in conditions when universities, business and science cooperate. Ukrainian universities should become a scientific platform. For the first time, during the years of independence, in 2016, Ukrainian universities were included in the list of one of the largest ratings of the world - Times Higher Education World University Rankings. Although it occurred exceptionally due to expanding of the list from the top 400 out of 41 countries to the top 800 out of 70 countries. The main criteria of evaluation of the situation in the field of science in any country are primarily the expenses of the state on research and development projects, the presence of high-tech companies on the market, the quality and availability of higher education, the number of patents and scientific researches. As these values are still far from the global standards, the outflow of young talented people from the country, the aging of scientists, and the lack of scientific progress are the evident results.

Another way of obtaining financial autonomy for higher educational institutions, which is proposed in the framework of the draft on improving of the educational activities in higher education, is the creation of “endowment”. Thus, in many European universities, it has been concluded long ago that it is impossible to keep and develop a university only at the expense of the students, which study on a tuition basis. In Harvard, for example, such a fund amounts to more than 40 billion dollars. It is a fund in which graduates or philanthropists temporarily invest: the university has no right to spend it, but can, for example, put the money on a deposit or invest it in the reliable financial instruments and use the interest afterwards. The interest becomes the property of the university [12]. Law “On Higher Education” of 2014 also provides for such a mechanism, but there are no subordinate acts and no changes to the Tax Code regarding the functioning of these funds. This practically legitimizes corruption. The project of the new education reform does not specify who can act as a donor of the university, whether these are foreign investors, entrepreneurs, philanthropists, etc.

Another problem that needs to be solved within the framework of educational reform is the quantitative and qualitative composition of scientific and pedagogical staff of universities. The average age of higher school teachers is 50+, and an issue of attracting young teachers is crucial, especially in the case of teaching the natural sciences. Students want to see young teachers. However, the question of the quality of education will not be resolved by simply replacing the old teachers with the young ones. It is necessary to invest in development of professional level of the teacher. Once well-organized in terms of centralized economy, the system of advanced training and professional retraining must become history. However, a new system that meets the needs of a market economy has not yet been created in Ukraine. At the moment there are a number of local initiatives in Ukraine, which are aimed at improving the teaching skills, mastering new methods of working with the audience. They need to be studied and promoted. Different forums, trainings, seminars for teachers are regularly performed in each region. They are organized

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by both public organizations and local self-government bodies. Nevertheless, the area of the right skills' performers concentration, as well as how and how intensively they use these skills in their practice, and whether they are willing to share the knowledge to their colleagues, remains unknown. The new procedure of advanced training for pedagogical and scientific-pedagogical workers provides greater variety of choice of providers of the corresponding services [13]. However, sometimes it can be rather difficult to choose the right provider. This function could be performed by a portal, with the help of which a person can quickly find out where within the limits of the city or the region he/she can improve his/her qualification, and a separate teacher or university administration decide to accept the proposed choice afterwards. In addition, it is possible to open the ability for teachers to conduct independent professional activities. These activities can be the following: to be the coach for colleagues in the framework of advanced training programs, to develop methodical materials and study guides. Such possibilities will help to improve the qualitative indicators for university teachers and will encourage the most qualified teachers to remain in their occupation.

3 Conclusion

After the declaration of Ukraine's independence, the education has been declared as one of the priorities of social, economic, spiritual and cultural development of the society. The right to free personal development and education has been embodied in The Constitution of Ukraine. From this perspective, it is the extremely important to create the conditions for holistic development of the human being as a personality and society's ultimate value, his/her talents, intellectual, creative, and physical abilities, shaping values and competences required for successful self-realization, raising responsible citizens who can make an informed social choice [1]. After 28 years, the education problems remain the target of great interest for the national educational and pedagogic science and public practice. Most conspicuously the society spiritually and intellectually devolves as well as the state lags behind the progressive economically developed countries in cultural, technical and technological areas without the developed education system, the precise definition of its goals or the appropriate organization of education management.

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